

Acid-catalysed Condensation of Phenolic Compounds with Cinnamyl Alcohol. Synthesis of Flavans and Linear Pyranocoumarins

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Acid-catalysed condensation of 2-methylresorcinol (1) with cinnamyl alcohol gave 2-4. The flavan (3) has been used for the synthesis of dihydropyranocoumarins (5, 10 and 14) which on dehydrogenation with DDQ gave the pyranocoumarins (8, 12 and 15, respectively).

3,4-Dihydro-2-phenyl-2H-1-benzopyrans (also known as flavans) have been reported for their biological activities¹. These can also be used as an intermediate for the synthesis of flav-3-enes and flavylum salts. We report here the acid-catalysed condensation of some phenolic compounds with cinnamyl alcohol leading to one-step synthesis of flavans, and these have been used as synthons for some coumarin derivatives which may be of biological interest since pyranocoumarins are well-known for their physiological properties².

The typical experimental procedure for acid-catalysed cinnamylation³ involves the addition of cinnamyl alcohol in benzene to a suspension of 2-methylresorcinol (1) in orthophosphoric acid (85%) and benzene with constant stirring for 6 h at 100-05° and stirring for further 12 h. Usual workup⁴ of the reaction mixture gave a residue containing three products (tlc) which were separated by column chromatography over silica gel and eluting with petroleum ether. The first fraction gave the negative ferric chloride test, and on the basis of its elemental analysis and spectral data it was assigned the structure 3,4,6,7-tetrahydro-10-methyl-2,8-diphenyl-2H,8H-benzo[1,2-b:5,4-b']dipyran (2). The second fraction, (major) gave positive ferric chloride test, and on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral data it was assigned the structure 3,4-dihydro-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-2-phenyl-2H-1-benzopyran (3). The third fraction also gave positive ferric chloride test and showed introduction of one cinnamyl unit by the elemental analysis. The ¹H nmr spectrum indicated it to be an open-chain compound, and hence it was assigned the structure 2,4-dihydroxy-3-methylcinnamylbenzene (4), which was further confirmed by its cyclisation with orthophosphoric acid to 3.

Pechman condensation⁴ of 3 with malic acid in the presence of concentrated H₂SO₄ gave a light yellow solid which was assigned the structure 6,7-dihydro-10-methyl-8-phenyl-2H,8H-benzo[1,2-b:5,4-b']dipyran-2-one (5) on the basis of its elemental

analysis and spectral data. The structure 5 was further confirmed by comparison (m.p., m.m.p. and co-ir) with an authentic sample which was prepared as follows. Acid-catalysed cinnamylation³ of 2,4-dihydroxy-3-methylbenzaldehyde (6) with cinnamyl alcohol gave only one product which was assigned the structure 6-formyl-3,4-dihydro-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-2-phenyl-2H-1-benzopyran (7), which on Perkin condensation⁴ with potassium acetate and acetic anhydride at 170-80° for 48 h gave 5 in 64% yield. Final dehydrogenation of 5 with 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyanobenzoquinone⁵ (DDQ) in anhydrous benzene at the reflux temperature for 100 h gave 10-methyl-8-phenyl-2H,8H-benzo[1,2-b:5,4-b']dipyran-2-one (8). Compound 7 was also dehydrogenated with DDQ⁵ to give 6-formyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-2-phenyl-2H-1-benzopyran (9).

Similarly, Pechman condensation⁴ of 3 with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of concentrated H₂SO₄ gave 6,7-dihydro-4,10-dimethyl-8-phenyl-2H,8H-benzo[1,2-b:5,4-b']dipyran-2-one (10). The structure 10 was confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample prepared by Witting reaction⁶ of 6-acetyl-3,4-dihydro-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-2-phenyl-2H-1-benzopyran⁷ (11) with ethoxycarbonylmethyl-entriphenylphosphorane. Compound 10 was dehydrogenated with DDQ⁵ to give 4,10-dimethyl-8-phenyl-2H,8H-benzo[1,2-b:5,4-b']dipyran-2-one (12). The acetylchroman (11) was also dehydrogenated with DDQ⁵ to give 6-acetyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-2-phenyl-2H-1-benzopyran (13).

Finally, the condensation of 3 (1 g) with ethyl benzoylacetate (1.2 ml) in absolute ethanol (5 ml) in presence of dry HCl gas at 0-10° and after the usual workup⁴ of the reaction mixture gave 6,7-dihydro-10-methyl-4,8-diphenyl-2H,8H-benzo[1,2-b:5,4-b']dipyran-2-one (14). The structure 14 was confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample prepared by acid-catalysed cinnamylation³ of 2,4-dihydroxy-3-methylbenzophenone⁸ (16) with cinnamyl alcohol, followed by Perkin condensation⁹ with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride of the

formed 6-benzoyl-3,4-dihydro-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-2-phenyl-2H-1-benzopyran (17). Compound 17 was dehydrogenated with DDQ⁵ to give 6-benzoyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-2-phenyl-2H-1-benzopyran (18). Dihydropyranocoumarin 14 was also dehydrogenated with DDQ⁵ to give 10-methyl-4,8-diphenyl-2H, 8H-benzo[1,2-b : 5,4-b']dipyran-2-one (15). All these structures were assigned on the basis of their elemental analysis and spectral data.

Attempts to dehydrogenate 3 with DDQ were unsuccessful; the reaction gave a mixture of products which were difficult to separate.

Experimental

General procedure. Condensation of 1 with cinnamyl alcohol (Formation of 2, 3, 4): A solution of cinnamyl alcohol (1.3 ml) in benzene (5 ml) was added to a suspension of 2-methylresorcinol (1 : 1 g) in orthophosphoric acid (85%; 4 ml) and benzene (5 ml) with constant stirring for 6 h at 100–05°. Stirring was continued for further 12 h and ether (25 ml) added. The resulting solid was washed successively with sodium bicarbonate (5%) and water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent distilled off to give a residue, which gave three fractions on column chromatography over silica gel and eluting the column with petroleum ether.

Fraction A: 3,4,6,7-Tetrahydro-10-methyl-2,8-diphenyl-2H, 8H-benzo[1,2-b : 5,4-b']dipyran (2): It was obtained as light pink oil (8%) (Found : C, 84.40; H, 6.85. C₂₅H₂₄O₂ requires : C, 84.27; H, 6.74%); δ (CDCl₃) 1.98 (4H, m, H-3 and H-7), 2.29 (3H, s, 10-OCH₃), 3.00 (4H, m, H-4 and H-6), 5.05 (2H, dd, *J* 11 and 4 Hz, H-2 and H-8), 6.52 (1H, s, H-5) and 7.10–7.38 (10H, m, 2 × C₆H₅).

Fraction B: 3,4-Dihydro-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-2-

phenyl-2H-1-benzopyran (3): It was obtained as pink plates (50%) m.p. 62–3° (Found : C, 80.21; H, 6.81. C₁₆H₁₆O₂ requires : C, 80.00; H, 6.67%); δ (CDCl₃) 1.91–2.20 (5H, m, H-3 and 8-CH₃), 2.65 (2H, m, H-4), 4.98 (1H, dd, *J* 11 and 4 Hz, H-2), 5.21 (1H, s, exchangeable with D₂O, 7-OH), 6.30 and 6.65 (each 1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-5 and H-6) and 7.25 (5H, s, C₆H₅). **Fraction C: 2,4-Dihydroxy-3-methylcinnamylbenzene (4):** It was obtained as colourless needles (20%), m.p. 93–4° (Found : C, 80.14; H, 6.76. C₁₆H₁₆O₂ requires : C, 80.00; H, 6.67%); δ (CDCl₃) 2.12 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.48 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz, CH₂CH=CH), 4.85 and 5.05 (each s, each 1H, exchangeable with D₂O, 2 × -OH), 6.35 (3H, m, H-5 and CH₂CHCH), 6.84 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-6) and 7.15–7.40 (6H, m, CH₂CH=CH and C₆H₅).

Following the same procedure of cinnamylation, compounds 7 and 17 were obtained: 2, light yellow needles (78%), m.p. 118° (Found : C, 76.24; H, 6.14. C₁₇H₁₆O₃ requires : C, 76.12; H, 5.97%); δ (CDCl₃) 2.02–2.10 (5H, m, H-3 and 8-CH₃), 2.80 (2H, m, H-4), 5.15 (1H, dd, *J* 11 and 4 Hz, H-2), 7.10 (1H, s, H-5), 7.40 (5H, s, C₆H₅), 9.65 (1H, s, CHO) and 13.20 (1H, s, exchangeable with D₂O, 7-OH); 17, light yellow needles (75%), m.p. 127–28° (Found : C, 80.37; H, 5.94. C₂₃H₂₀O₃ requires : C, 80.23; H, 5.81%); δ (CDCl₃) 1.98 (2H, m, H-3), 2.15 (3H, s, 8-CH₃), 2.88 (2m, m, H-4), 5.11 (1H, dd, *J* 11 and 4 Hz, H-2), 7.10–7.70 (11H, m, H-5 and 2 × C₆H₅) and 13.00 (1H, s, exchangeable with D₂O, 7-OH).

General procedure. Formation of 6,7-dihydro-10-methyl-8-phenyl-2H, 8H-benzo[1,2-b : 5,4-b']dipyran-2-one (5): 3 and malic acid (1 g) were powdered into an intimate mixture, and concentrated H₂SO₄ (4 ml) was added and the mixture heated on a steam-bath for 2 h. The cooled reaction mixture was then poured on crushed ice and extracted with ether. The ether layer was washed successively with 5% sodium carbonate (2 × 10 ml) and water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and distilled to obtain the solid product which was crystallised from petroleum ether as light yellow needles (5; 64%), m.p. 185–86° (Found : C, 78.21; H, 5.66. C₁₉H₁₈O₃ requires : C, 78.08; H, 5.48%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1710 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 1.90 (2H, m, H-7), 2.22 (3H, s, 10-CH₃), 3.05 (2H, m, H-6), 5.15 (1H, dd, *J* 11 and 4 Hz, H-8), 6.13 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, H-3), 7.00 (1H, s, H-5), 7.51 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, H-4) and 7.65 (5H, s, C₆H₅); compound 10, colourless needles (76%), m.p. 125–26° (Found : C, 78.56; H, 5.94. C₂₀H₁₈O₃ requires : C, 78.43; H, 5.88%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1690 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 2.00 (2H, m, H-7), 2.30 and 2.35 (each 3H, s, 2 × CH₃), 2.90 (2H, m, H-6), 5.20 (1H, dd, *J* 11 and 4 Hz, H-8), 6.12 (1H, s, H-3), 7.21 (1H, s, H-5) and 7.45 (5H, s, C₆H₅).

6,7-Dihydro-10-methyl-4,8-diphenyl-2H, 8H-benzo[1,2-b : 5,4-b']dipyran-2-one (14): A rapid stream of dry HCl gas was passed (5–6 h) into a cooled (0–10°) solution of 11 (1 g) and ethylbenzoyl

acetate (1.2 ml) in absolute ethanol (5 ml). The mixture was allowed to stand in a refrigerator for 48 h and then poured on crushed ice. The reaction mixture was worked up as in the case of **5** and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as colourless needles (**14**; 65%), m.p. 174–75 (Found: C, 81.64; H, 5.55. $C_{25}H_{20}O_8$ requires: C, 81.52; H, 5.45%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1700 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ ($CDCl_3$ +TFA) 1.85 (2H, m, H-7), 2.10 (3H, s, 10- CH_3), 2.85 (2H, m, H-6), 5.15 (1H, dd, J 11 and 4 Hz, H-8), 6.30 (1H, s, H-3) and 6.81–7.40 (1H, m, H-5 and $2 \times C_6H_5$).

General procedure for compounds 8, 12, 15, 9, 13 and 18: Compound **5** (0.1 g) was refluxed with DDQ (0.1 g) in anhydrous benzene (10 ml) for 100 h. The solution was then filtered, washed with 10% sodium carbonate solution and water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated. The resulting solid was crystallised from benzene–petroleum ether to give colourless needles (**8**; 60%), m.p. 104–05° (Found: C, 78.78; H, 4.85. $C_{19}H_{14}O_8$ requires: C, 78.62; H, 4.83%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1695 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.20 (3H, s, 10- CH_3), 5.15 (1H, dd, J 11 and 4 Hz, H-8), 5.54 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-7), 6.10 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-3), 6.20 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-6), 7.10 (1H, s, H-5), 7.42 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-4) and 7.52 (5H, s, C_6H_5); **12**, colourless needles (62%), m.p. 129–30° (Found: C, 79.04; H, 5.40. $C_{20}H_{16}O_8$ requires: C, 78.95; H, 5.26%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1700 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.20 and 2.32 (each 3H, s, $2 \times CH_3$), 5.12 (1H, dd, J 11 and 4 Hz, H-8), 5.58 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-7), 6.10 (1H, s, H-3), 6.28 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-6), 7.00 (1H, s, H-5) and 7.35 (5H, s, C_6H_5); **15**, colourless needles, (55%), m.p. 145–46° (Found: C, 82.12; H, 5.08. $C_{22}H_{18}O_8$ requires: C, 81.97; H, 4.92%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1705 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.15 (3H, s, 10- CH_3), 5.2 (1H, dd, J 11 and 4 Hz, H-8), 5.55 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-7), 6.10 (1H, s, H-3), 6.22 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-6), 6.89

(1H, s, H-5) and 7.08–7.37 (10H, m, $2 \times C_6H_5$); **9**, colourless needles, (50%), m.p. 64–5° (Found: C, 76.82; H, 5.38. $C_{17}H_{14}O_8$ requires: C, 76.69; H, 5.26%); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.10 (3H, s, 8- CH_3), 5.20 (1H, dd, J 11 and 5 Hz, H-2), 5.60 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-3), 6.20 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-4), 7.10 (1H, s, H-5), 7.40 (5H, s, C_6H_5), 9.60 (1H, s, CHO) and 13.28 (1H, s, exchangeable with D_2O , 7-OH); **13**, colourless needles (60%), m.p. 110–11° (Found: C, 77.22; H, 5.80. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8$ requires: C, 77.14; H, 5.17%); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.15 (3H, s, 8- CH_3), 2.50 (3H, s, $COCH_3$), 5.15 (1H, dd, J 11 and 4 Hz, H-2), 5.48 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-3), 6.17 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-4), 7.15 (1H, s, H-5), 7.35 (5H, s, C_6H_5) and 12.80 (1H, s, exchangeable with D_2O , 7-OH); **18**, colourless needles (52%), m.p. 135–36° (52%) (Found: C, 80.84; H, 5.46. $C_{23}H_{18}O_8$ requires: C, 80.70; H, 5.26%); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.20 (3H, s, 1- CH_3), 5.15 (1H, dd, J 11 and 4 Hz, H-2), 5.55 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-3), 6.26 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-4), 7.18–7.85 (11H, m, H-5 and $2 \times C_6H_5$) and 13.50 (1H, s, exchangeable with D_2O , 7-OH).

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